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List of Acronyms

BepiC	BepiColombo
D	Deliverable
EPHIN	Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument
ERNE	Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment
G4VM	Geant4 Virtual Machine
GCR	Galactic Cosmic Ray
GDML	Geometry Description Markup Language
GEANT	GEometry ANd Tracking
HET	High Energy Telescope
SIXS	Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SoIO	Solar Orbiter
SPEARHEAD	SPeCification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data
SQ	Science Question
TO	Technical Objective
WP	Work Package
KET	Kiel Electron Telescope
COSPIN	COsmic ray and Solar Particle INstrumentation
PM	Photomultiplier
SFS	Selected Flight Spare
SFM	Selected Flight Model

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document reports on the development of the [GEANT4](#) model for Ulysses/Kiel Electron Telescope ([KET](#)) and describes the components used in the Geometry Description Markup Language ([GDML](#)) schema to implement the geometry and material composition of the instrument in [GEANT4](#).

This document presents the development of a [GEANT4](#) simulation model specifically for the Ulysses/Kiel Electron Telescope ([KET](#)) instrument. It describes how the instrument's geometry and material composition were implemented using the [GDML](#) schema within the [GEANT4](#) framework. The use of [GDML](#) ensures accurate and structured representation of the physical setup for simulation purposes.

The model is released as part of the Geant4 Virtual Machine ([G4VM](#)), as referenced in deliverable Deliverable ([D](#))6.2, providing a readily accessible and portable environment for running simulations. This distribution facilitates use by other researchers without requiring complex setup or configuration.

This work is a continuation and complement to the series of [GEANT4](#) models developed under the SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data ([SPEARHEAD](#)) project. It follows on from deliverable [D2.1](#) – [GEANT4](#) Models, Part I, which was submitted in month 12 of the project's timeline. Together, these efforts aim to create a comprehensive and modular library of simulation tools for space science instrumentation.

1 Introduction

SPEARHEAD will provide answers to three Science Questions (SQs):

1. How are protons accelerated beyond 100 MeV and electrons beyond 1 MeV in solar eruptions?
2. What are the release times and spectral characteristics of near-relativistic particles from solar eruptions?
3. How do coronal and interplanetary structures affect the transport processes of very high energetic particles?

To enable the scientific data analysis SPEARHEAD has three Technical Objective (TO):

1. Determining the response functions of a large number of spacecraft instruments to derive high-energy particle fluxes from observations at unprecedented accuracy releasing revised and completely new datasets
2. Performing cross-calibration of datasets measured by science-grade and monitoring instruments to enable the use of monitoring data for scientific analyses
3. Combining high-energy particle and context observations together with modeling of plasma structures for easier in-depth analysis of solar eruptions, quantifying their effect and delivering them to the community.

Hereby Work Package (WP)2 directly addresses TO1 and supports TO2.

Efficiency computation for space particle instruments like Electron, Proton and Helium Instrument (EPHIN) (Müller-Mellin et al. 1995) aboard Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) and EPHIN aboard Chandra, SOHO/Energetic and Relativistic Nuclei and Electron experiment (ERNE) (Torsti et al. 1995), Solar Orbiter (SolO)/High Energy Telescope (HET) (Rodríguez-Pacheco et al. 2020), BepiColombo (BepiC)/Solar Intensity X-ray and particle Spectrometer (SIXS) (Huovelin et al. 2020) as well as Ulysses/KET (Simpson et al. 1992) involves quantifying the instrument's ability to detect and measure particles accurately in a space environment. In more detail:

- Particle measurements consist of a set of measured quantities (like energy losses, photon detection etc.) typically quantified as count rates C .
- At a given time t the instrument is embedded in a radiation environment consisting of different ions, electrons, and photons that are the unknown physical quantities $J_\alpha(E, \omega, \mathbf{x}, t)$ to be derived. Herein E , ω , \mathbf{x} , and α are the kinetic Energy, the incoming direction, the location, and particle species, respectively.
- Both are interlinked by the Sullivan (Sullivan 1971) equation:

$$C(\mathbf{x}, t_0) = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} dt \int_S \hat{\mathbf{r}} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\sigma} \int_\Omega d\omega \int_0^\infty dE \sum_\alpha \varepsilon_\alpha(E, \boldsymbol{\sigma}, \omega, t) J_\alpha(E, \omega, \mathbf{x}, t) \quad (1)$$

with:

J_α = spectral intensity of particle α

ε_α = detection efficiency of particle type α

t = time

t_0 = time at start of observation

T = total observation time

$d\sigma$ = element of surface area of the last telescope sensor to be penetrated

S = total area of the last telescope sensor

$d\omega$ = element of solid angle

Ω = domain of ω ; this is limited by the other telescope sensors

\mathbf{x} = spatial coordinate of the telescope

$\hat{\mathbf{f}}$ = unit vector in direction ω

$\hat{\mathbf{f}} \cdot d\sigma$ = effective element of area looking into ω

Efficiency typically depends on factors such as the geometry, material properties, detection mechanisms, and energy thresholds of the instrument.

In order to compute efficiencies, Monte-Carlo simulations utilizing the [GEANT4](#) toolkit ([Agostinelli et al. 2003](#)) are performed to model the particle interactions with the instrument and the total efficiency (see [D2.3](#); [Köberle et al. \(2025\)](#) for further details). However, the computations need to be validated by comparing with calibration efforts using known particle sources or different instrumentation (for details see [D3.1](#); [Heber et al. \(2024\)](#)).

[D2.4](#) sets the foundation for the subsequent deliverable [D2.5](#) (Delivery of the validated response function for Ulysses/KET) by providing and implementing an accurate model of the [KET](#).

2 The Kiel Electron Telescope

The [KET](#) onboard the Ulysses spacecraft is part of the Ulysses COsmic ray and Solar Particle INstrumentation ([COSPIN](#)) and was designed to study energetic charged particles in interplanetary space. Its primary objectives include measuring the energy spectra of electrons, protons, and helium across a wide energy range. The main objective was to measure the electron fluxes between a few MeV and below several GeV (for details see [Simpson et al. 1992](#)). To allow charge-sign-dependent studies on the solar modulation of Galactic Cosmic Ray ([GCR](#)), it also provided measurements of proton and helium fluxes in several energy windows between a few MeV and above 2 GeV/amu (see studies of electrons and protons at a rigidity of about 2.5 GV by [Rastoin et al. 1996](#); [Ferrando et al. 1996](#); [Heber et al. 2002, 2003, 2009](#)).

The detector system, illustrated in the left panel of [Fig. 1](#), consists of two main components:

The entrance telescope combines a Cerenkov detector made of silica-aerogel (**C1** in [Fig. 1](#)) positioned between two semiconductor detectors (**D1** and **D2**). Together with the anticoincidence, this configuration defines the geometry of the system and selects particles with velocities exceeding $\beta > 0.938$.

The calorimeter (C2) is a lead-fluoride (PbF₂) crystal with a thickness of 2.5 radiation lengths, which functions as a Cerenkov detector where electron showers develop. **C2** is surrounded by an anticoincidence to reject particles that penetrate **C2** not within the opening angle defined by the entrance telescope. Lastly, a scintillator (**S2**) detects particles, i.e. electrons that are not absorbed by **C2**.

3 Description of GDML file

The construction of the [GDML](#) built upon a preexisting [GEANT3](#) model of the Selected Flight Model ([SFM](#)) shown in the right panel of [Figure 1](#).

The original [SFM](#) was replaced by the Selected Flight Spare ([SFS](#)) due to better light collection of the [SFS](#)

Figure 1: Left: Sketch of the KET (from Dunzlaff (2012)) Right: GEANT3 model of the KET (Heber 1997)

(see Sierks (1988)). The two models differ slightly in dimensions, e.g., the radii of the semiconductors **D1** and **D2** as can be seen in Figures 3 and 4 shown in the appendix. The GDML model was adapted accordingly. In addition, a detailed representation of the diffusion box was implemented which scatters the Cerenkov light produced in the **C2** through a hole in the **S2** towards the Photomultiplier (**PM**)2. In order to measure particles that escape through the gap resulting from the addition of the diffusion box, the extension of the **S2** was introduced. A final addition was made in the form of the quartz/glass window of the **PM2** to account for additional Cerenkov light produced therein by particles traversing the instrument with an angle of $\approx 17^\circ$. A visualization of the final GEANT4 model can be seen in Figure 2.

The GDML file of Ulysses/KET is provided in the scope of the G4VM via the SPEARHEAD GitHub repository (D6.2; Gieseler et al. (2024)), available at <https://github.com/spearhead-he/G4VM>, with the aim of making the new GEANT4 model readily accessible.

The G4VM repository contains one main file of the instrument named `ket.gdml` within the KET folder. The GDML file follows the general structure described in Section 2.2 of D2.1 Köberle et al. (2024); however, for readability, groups of components are outsourced to separate folders and imported as entities at the beginning of the main GDML file. The following is a description of the groups and their content.

Aluminum contains parts of the housing made of aluminum

Cerenkov contains the cerenkov detectors **C1** and **C2** plus the quartz/glass components of **PM2**

Delrin contains the housing components made of delrin

Foils contains the kapton and aluminum foils

Scintillators contains the anti-coincidence as **S2** scintillators

SSDs contains the **D1** and **D2** detectors

Figure 2: Visualization of the final [GEANT4](#) model.

4 Conclusions

The reliability of energetic particle measurements in space depends on several factors. These include the sensitivity and calibration of the detectors used, the shielding of the instruments against background radiation, and the stability of the spacecraft's environment. To enable scientific data analysis of Ulysses/[KET](#) data within [SPEARHEAD](#), a determination and validation of the response function is needed. Essential for the process is a detailed model of the particle instrument.

In this deliverable, we successfully implemented the sensor geometry of Ulysses/[KET](#) in the [G4VM](#) virtual machine ([Gieseler et al. 2024](#)). This model will be used in [D2.5](#) in order to compute the energy response functions that are needed as input to the bow-tie tool described in [D6.2](#) ([Gieseler et al. 2024](#)) and provided via the [SPEARHEAD GitHub](#)^a

^a<https://github.com/spearhead-he/bowtie>

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Figure 4: Drawing of the SFS (from Iwers (2000))